

1 **Near-optimal coverage trajectories for image** 2 **mosaicing using a mini quad-rotor over irregular-** 3 **shaped fields**

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9 **Abstract:** Aerial images are useful tools for farmers who practise precision agriculture. The
10 difficulty in taking geo-referenced high-resolution aerial images in a narrow time window
11 considering weather restrictions and the high cost of commercial services are the main drawbacks
12 of these techniques. In this paper, a useful tool to obtain aerial images by using low cost
13 Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) is presented. The proposed system allows farmers to easily
14 define and execute an aerial image coverage mission by using geographic information system
15 (GIS) tools in order to obtain mosaics made of high-resolution images. The system computes a
16 complete path for the UAV by taking into account the on-board camera features once the image
17 requirements and area to be covered are defined. This work introduces a full four-step procedure:
18 mission definition, automatic path planning, mission execution and mosaic generation.

19 **Keywords:** *aerial images, mosaicing, coverage path planning, aerial robots,*
20 *mission planner, remote sensing.*

21

22 **Introduction**

23 High availability aerial vehicles equipped with inexpensive and
24 lightweight sensors have become suitable remote sensing (RS) tools, overcoming
25 the deficiencies of other RS options, such as satellites or airplanes. Nowadays,
26 they are able to provide an affordable, adaptable and fast data acquisition tool for
27 agricultural purposes.

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1 Currently, aerial vehicles (mainly planes) are employed in agriculture for
2 crop observation and map generation through imaging surveys (Johnson et al.
3 2003, Herwitz et al. 2004). The maps are usually built by stitching a set of geo-
4 referenced images (e.g. orthophotos) through mosaicing procedures. These maps
5 give detailed information about biophysical parameters of the crop field. The
6 agricultural experiments reported with aerial vehicles mainly use waypoint-based
7 navigation features (Johnson et al. 2003, Berni et al. 2009, Nebiker et al. 2008),
8 where the aerial vehicles navigate autonomously through a trajectory pre-defined
9 by a set of points in the environment.

10 Therefore, the aerial vehicle usually has to scan the full area by following
11 a continuous and smooth trajectory and, at the same time, avoiding areas or
12 parcels that are not subjects of interest.

13 In the light of the studies mentioned above, it can be concluded that two
14 strongly coupled aspects have to be defined in order to accomplish the full
15 mission: the type of UAV platform and the mission-planning solver.

16 Regarding UAV platforms, it needs to be pointed out that the use of planes
17 not only intensifies the difficulty in calculating optimal trajectories but also
18 eliminates the possibility of taking several images from the same point. In
19 addition to this, the fact of taking pictures in motion reduces the possibility of
20 operating in poor light scenarios, requiring high-speed image capture. Two further
21 drawbacks in using planes compared to other vehicles are the reduction of
22 positioning accuracy and the inability to take off or land in small spaces. On the
23 other hand, although helicopters are a better option with regard to path planning
24 and performance, they are highly complex and require exhaustive maintenance
25 and extensive training for operators in order to avoid critical damage and
26 accidents.

27 Quad-rotors are a novel platform that rely on the advantages of helicopters
28 and bring together the best features for outdoor missions. This mini platform has
29 four electric rotors but, in contrast to typical helicopters, there is no pitch blade
30 variation. Therefore, changes in attitude or elevation are obtained only by
31 controlling the speed of the four motors independently. As a result, quad-rotors
32 turn out to be much easier to setup and operate than helicopters.

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1 Additionally, considering safety aspects, the risk of material and physical injuries
2 is less likely than with other types of mini UAVs. Finally, it is worth mentioning
3 that quad-rotors are much cheaper than other vehicles in terms of maintenance and
4 parts.

5 Currently, quad-rotors are widely available. Their high maneuverability
6 allows reducing the time to complete their operations. As previously mentioned,
7 path planning also has to consider suitable areas for taking off and landing to
8 fulfill all requirements (safety margins, sufficient space for operation, pick up and
9 drop ability, accessibility).

10 In order to manage these requirements, coverage path planning (CPP)
11 techniques have been applied to solve the problem. CPP is a sub-topic of motion
12 planning, which deals with methods to determine a path that ensures complete
13 coverage (e.g. back and forth motions) for a robot in a free workspace.

14 Since the robot has to fly over all points in the free workspace, the CPP
15 problem is related to the covering salesman problem (CSP), a NP (non-
16 deterministic polynomial with very hard time restrictions) problem (Choset 2001).
17 Coverage path planning with Unmanned Aerial vehicles (UAV) was discussed by
18 Jiao et al. (2010) and Maza and Ollero (2007) where exact cell decomposition
19 methods were proposed to break down a polygonal area.

20 Although the cited authors used exact cell decomposition, their approaches
21 addressed mainly decomposition of areas and coverage with back and forth
22 motions. This study addresses the problem of covering an entire farm site with a
23 vertical takeoff and landing aerial robot provided with way-point navigation
24 capability. Therefore, an off-line mission planner has been developed for
25 commercial off-the-shelf aerial robots. The method is able to compute a coverage
26 path that is restricted to the minimum number of turns, avoidable cells and
27 predefined starting and goal positions.

28 Most UAVs employed in agricultural tasks are off-the-shelf platforms with
29 an autopilot that is able to perform a flight following a way-point list. The work
30 presented aims to help the operator in optimally defining a coverage mission
31 under some usual restrictions. The mission planner computes a coverage path in a
32 given target area and *a priori* information. Since the output of the planner is
33 retrieved as a set of geographic co-ordinates, the operator can use it with any type

1 of aerial robot with way-point navigation features. Thus, the platform can be used
2 by any user regardless of the level of knowledge about the system.

3 **Previous work**

4 In the last decade, some research has enhanced the task of acquiring aerial
5 images by using a mini aerial vehicle. At the beginning, this task was difficult
6 because researchers had to build the aerial platforms from basic leisure radio
7 controlled models. These conversions were often time consuming. Moreover, the
8 robustness of the final prototype did not comply with the required performance.
9 Some of those achievements can be found in Xiang and Tian (2011).

10 Those problems have been solved with the progress in miniaturization and
11 reduction in the cost of the system. The mini aerial vehicle market has many well-
12 conceived off-the-shelf platforms available, which are ready to fly (both manually
13 and using way-point navigation) and are high-level programmable (Hunt et al.
14 2010, Valente et al. 2011b)

15 Most of the reported studies have been concerned with the feasibility of
16 the platform to acquire images or the techniques for image processing (Lelong et
17 al. 2008, Berni et al. 2009, Hunt et al. 2010). Very few studies have focused on
18 the ability to optimize the image survey trajectory, which is a step forward in
19 optimizing the overall mission.

20 In a previous study (Valente et al. 2011a), a feasible approach to survey an
21 agricultural field subject to several constraints was proposed. It described how a
22 coverage mission could be achieved in three steps (1. Offline definition of
23 workspace and acquisition of data from the GIS environment. 2. Insertion and
24 computation of coverage path based on the previous data. 3. Execution of the
25 mission). However, no experimental results about the coverage mission were
26 presented.

27 In this paper, experimental results are presented and they include a brief
28 analysis of the results. The experimental results were obtained in a large vineyard
29 parcel that was surveyed with a quad-rotor carrying a low cost digital camera. A
30 low altitude flight (<100m) was carried out in order to obtain images to build a
31 map by using mosaicing techniques.

32

1 **Mission definition**

2 The first step of the aerial mission is the setup of vehicle and base station. In this
3 section, the components of the system are briefly described.

4 **Instruments and methods**

5 The system has been split into three interconnected elements: aerial vehicle,
6 camera and communication resources.

7 Maneuverability is a critical factor for the aerial vehicle. A vehicle able to
8 move from one waypoint to another in minimal time and having the capability for
9 hovering and backward movement is required. Additionally, an important
10 capability for a successful execution of the mission is the possibility of hovering
11 (staying in a determined position for some undefined time). It should also be taken
12 into account that the mission is performed in outdoor scenarios. These missions
13 require robust systems, capable of working under adverse weather conditions.

14 Multi-rotor systems comply with all these characteristics: The multiple
15 motors of quad-rotors or hexacopters provide enough lift, not only to carry the
16 payload, but also to hold it in different poses while performing very stable flights.
17 At the same time, the robustness and reliability of the system are improved when
18 uncomplicated mechanisms are used. Therefore, a four-propeller solution was
19 selected as flying platform. Pelican quad-rotor from Ascending Technologies
20 GmbH, which is a German company (see Figure 1), has been used in order to
21 perform the experiments. It has the following features:

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Fig.1: Quad-rotor with the embedded on-board camera.

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- 2 • Maximum speed: 50km/h
- 3 • Maximum windload: 36km/h
- 4 • Maximum flight time: 20mins
- 5 • Maximum payload: 500g

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7 The second module is the image acquisition system. As previously
8 mentioned, the drone's main mission consists of placing the camera in a set of
9 defined locations. It requires an integration process in order to incorporate the
10 camera in the system, both mechanically and electronically: On the one hand, the
11 mechanical integration aims to hold the camera at the front side of the drone,
12 pointing downwards. It has entailed the design of a specific element, ergonomic
13 and robust enough to guarantee the security of the assembly. Nevertheless, this
14 necessary component places the camera away from the drones' center of gravity
15 (CoG). Due to this, the quad-rotor attitude should be projected so as to estimate its
16 effect on deviation in the acquired image by using Euler angles. Equation 1
17 presents the required transformations:

$$T = Rot_{roll}(\alpha) * Rot_{pitch}(\beta) * Transl(P_{x,y,z}) =$$
$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos(\beta) & 0 & \sin(\beta) & P_x \\ \sin(\alpha) * \sin(\beta) & \cos(\alpha) * \cos(\beta) & -\sin(\alpha) * \cos(\beta) & P_y \\ t - \cos(\alpha) * \sin(\beta) & \sin(\alpha) * \cos(\beta) & \cos(\alpha) * \cos(\beta) & P_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

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19 where α and β represent the roll and pitch absolute angles, and $P_{x,y,z}$ is a
20 three co-ordinates vector, which describes the distance from the CoG of the quad-
21 rotor to the CoG of the camera. In this study, this equation should be substituted
22 with the following values: $P_x = 0m$, $P_y = 97mm$ and $P_z = -20mm$.

23

24 The selection of the camera should also be considered. In this sense, the
25 mission sets several requirements: Firstly, the weight has to be as low as possible.
26 Furthermore, the lenses should be able to work in poor light scenarios. It will
27 therefore need large sensors, which are two conflicting requirements. The images
28 are captured whilst the drone is in motion. Therefore, a fast shutter speed is
required in order to minimize this effect and obtain clearer and sharper

1 photographs. Nevertheless, the higher the shutter speed is, the lower the
2 illumination of the scene. Therefore, high brightness lens are required to
3 compensate for this effect. Since a trade-off was required, a PENTAX Option S1
4 has finally been chosen. It has the following characteristics:

- 5 • Dimensions: 90 x 54 x 20mm
- 6 • Weight: 110g
- 7 • Lens: 28-140mm (35mm equiv.). f/3.9-5.7
- 8 • ISO sensitivity: 64 to 6400 ISO
- 9 • Maximum image resolution: 4288x3216pixels
- 10 • Resolution: 14M pixel
- 11 • Sensor: CCD 1/2.3in
- 12 • Maximum shutter speed: 1/6000s
- 13 • Image stabilizer: Yes (optical)
- 14 • Video recording: HD 720p

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16 Finally, when evaluating and designing the system, the control modes and
17 the command exchange protocol should be taken into account. Thus, a remote
18 control to operate the camera is required. PENTAX Option S1 and its IR handler
19 have been analyzed. The camera's protocol has been decrypted (see figure 2) and
20 replicated in an on-board device. It uses an independent full-duplex XBee
21 channel, which is connected to the base station, in order to allow the camera to be
22 triggered both manually and automatically. In this second mode -the predefined
23 one-, the system analyzes the quad-rotor navigation data provided by the
24 controller, and commands the acquisition according to the quad-rotor position,
25 attitude and speed. Since the images are acquired only when the attitude values
26 are below a predefined threshold, a minimum error in the correspondence between
27 the images and the position where they were taken can be guaranteed.

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2 Fig. 2: IR remote control for PENTAX Option S1 triggering. The sample frequency is 38 KHz

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4 The integration -as well as the control-were implemented using the Robot
 5 Operating System (ROS) architecture and resources (Quigley et al. 2009). It
 6 allows using a modular implementation that directly connects the drone's
 7 navigation data with the triggering decider process. It also provides a fast
 8 response that enables quick geo-referencing by matching images with the
 9 navigation data.

10 **Workspace sampling**

11 The environment has been modeled through an approximate cellular
 12 decomposition following the taxonomy proposed by (Choset 2001), which means
 13 that the robot workspace is sampled as a regular grid. The grid-based
 14 representation with optimal dispersion is obtained by dividing the space into
 15 cubes and considering their centers as waypoints for the drones. This
 16 arrangement can be considered as a kind of Sukharev grid (LaValle 2006). It
 17 should be highlighted that exact cell decompositions such as trapezoidal
 18 decompositions are inefficient for aerial coverage, since the goal is to acquire a
 19 homogeneous sized set of samples with the same spatial resolution from the target
 20 environment. This is not possible to be obtained using a fix focal length camera as
 21 shown in figure3, where the exact cell decomposition on the right provides a set
 22 of irregular cells that do not correspond to the shape of an image frame. In this
 23 method, the cells homogeneity is not ensured.

24

Fig.3: An environment decomposed by two different methods. For each workspace, a cell is highlighted in green.

1 Grid-based representations provides a simple way to manage this problem,
 2 since the center of each cell is assumed to be a way-point, and the cell dimension
 3 is proportional to the image dimension obtained from the visual sensor.

4 The grid resolution is obtained through image requirements - resolution
 5 and overlapping - and the image sensor characteristics. The first step is to
 6 determine a desired spatial resolution (pixels/m). By using this parameter and the
 7 real resolution of the available camera, the cell dimension can be computed. This
 8 spatial resolution depends on the final use of the picture (water stress, weed
 9 detection, etc.). Since the real size of the cell and the dimensions of the ground are
 10 known, the number of cells (actually photographs) required to map the whole field
 11 can be easily computed. Finally, the last parameter to be computed is the flight
 12 altitude in order to ensure the cell dimensions (photograph dimensions projected
 13 from the ground). The aerial vehicle height above the ground can be computed
 14 through the relationship shown in Equation 2.

$$\frac{\tau_d}{\tau_h} = \frac{I_d}{l} \quad (2)$$

15 where τ_d , τ_h , I_d , l stand respectively for target dimension, target distance,
 16 image dimension, focal length of the camera (see figure 4). After that an offset
 17 $\delta < \theta$ is added to the computed co-ordinates in order to apply the overlapping rate.
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1 Fig.4: Aerial height computation during the mission. a) Ground cell dimensions and aerial vehicle
 2 height relationship. b) Image overlapping rates obtained with different δ .
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4 **Path generation**

5 After the mission definition previously addressed, the next step is to compute the
 6 aerial coverage trajectory. This step is mainly addressed by the mission planner:
 7 first, convert the decomposed workspace to a regular graph and then compute the
 8 coverage path by employing graph search approaches.

9 **Workspace to graph conversion**

10 Consider a square or rectangular area $\Phi \subset \mathbb{R}^2$ and approximately decomposed by
 11 a finite set of regular cells $C = \{c_1 \dots c_n\}$ in such way,

$$\Phi = \bigcup_{c \in C} c \quad (3)$$

12
 13 One of the big advantages of having a grid-based decomposition is that the
 14 robot workspace can be directly converted into a kind of unit distance graph,
 15 denoted as grid graph (see Figure 5), and that can be written as,

$$G_{\langle V, E \rangle}, \quad \text{where } v \equiv p, \quad v \in V \quad \text{and} \quad p \in \mathbf{P} \quad (4)$$

17 where V are the vertex, E the edges. \mathbf{P} is a discrete trajectory defined by
 18 way-points, such that,

$$\mathbf{P} = \bigcup_{p \in \mathbf{P}} p \quad (5)$$

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 20 Each vertex represents a way-point and each edge, the path between two way-
 21 points u and v such that $u \sim v$.
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Fig. 5: A Grid graph.

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3 Coverage path planning

4 Heuristic and non-heuristic algorithms have been employed to obtain a complete
5 coverage path with the minimum number of turns, subject to a pre-defined initial
6 and goal position and without re-visited points within the workspace.

7 The distance transform function is applied over the grid by employing a
8 Bread-first search (BFS) (LaValle 2006) on the graph induced by the
9 neighborhood adjacency of cells. As a result, the coverage path can be easily
10 found from any starting point within the environment to the goal cell by choosing
11 the nearest neighbor cell in gradient ascendant order instead of the common
12 descendant order.

13 Deep-limited search (DLS) (LaValle 2006) is used to build a tree with all
14 possible coverage paths in order to find a complete coverage path that passes
15 through all nodes in the adjacency graph only once. Using this approach, the
16 search length can be limited to the number of vertices, and consequently, the
17 search neither goes around in infinite cycles nor visits a node twice.

18 During the gradient tracking, the algorithm will find more than one
19 neighbor to choose from with the same potential weight. Additionally, the
20 bottleneck caused by the local minimum can also block the search. In order to
21 solve these issues, a backtracking procedure was employed.

22 Finally, the coverage path with the minimum number of turns is chosen by using
23 the following cost function,

$$24 \quad \Gamma = \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_k^{\{i\}}, \quad k \in \{135^\circ, 90^\circ, 45^\circ, 0^\circ\} \quad (6)$$

25 where,

$$26 \quad \gamma_{\pm 135^\circ} > \gamma_{\pm 90^\circ} > \gamma_{\pm 45^\circ} > \gamma_{0^\circ} \quad (7)$$

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The algorithm pseudo code is shown in Algorithm 1, where Φ is a field sampled in a finite number of way-points, \mathbf{P} is a complete coverage path.

Algorithm 1 Coverage path planning algorithm.

```
1: Initialize  $FiFo = \emptyset$   
2:  $G_{\langle V, E \rangle} \leftarrow ConvertToGraph(\Phi)$   
3:  $G'_{\langle V, E \rangle} \leftarrow Wavefront(G_{\langle V, E \rangle})$   
4: while  $\exists P \in \Phi$  do  
5:    $P \leftarrow DLS_w/Backtracking(G'_{\langle V, E \rangle})$   
6:    $FiFo \leftarrow FiFo + P$   
7: end while  
8:  $P^* \leftarrow \min(\Gamma(FiFo))$   
9: Return  $P^*$ 
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7 The gradient-based approach, although not ensuring an optimal solution,
8 provides a simple and a rapid way to obtain a near optimal coverage solution, in
9 both regular and irregular fields, with and without obstacles, subject to the
10 aforementioned restrictions.

11 Results

12 Finally, the mission execution is carried out. In this section, the experimental
13 results concerning the image survey mission with a quad-rotor carrying a digital
14 camera are presented. The agricultural field chosen to put the aforementioned
15 approach in practice is a vineyard parcel located in Belmonte de Tajo, near
16 Madrid, Spain. The agricultural field with irregular shape is shown in Figure 6.

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Fig.6: Vineyard parcel of area approximately 63765 m² (195x327m) and geographic co-ordinates 40°06'47.43"N and 3°17'02.33"W.

1 **Aerial Coverage**

2 In order to plan the coverage mission, a geo-referenced image from the target field
 3 should be obtained from a GIS database. The orthophoto used in planning the
 4 mission is depicted in Figure 7. The following areas have been delimited: 1)
 5 workspace boundaries (solid yellow), 2) field boundaries (solid blue), 3)
 6 undesired patches (dashed red). Further non-interest areas inside the workspace
 7 are pointed out with dashed red arrows.

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10 Fig. 7: Workspace definition inside the agricultural field.

11

12 The workspace is then decomposed considering its properties, the mosaic
 13 requirements and the digital camera parameters according to the methods
 14 described in the section Mission definition. Those values are summarized in table
 15 1.

16

17 Table 1: Mapping values considered in the workspace decomposition

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(a) Mosaic requirements

Spatial resolution	Image overlapping
10 mm/pixel	5%

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(b) Digital camera characteristics

Image resolution	I_d	l
10M (3216x3216 pixels)	35mm	50mm

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(c) Workspace size

Width	Length
195m	327m

The aforementioned values provide sufficient information to compute the number of cells in which the workspace is decomposed. The real size of each cell and the height above the ground are required to ensure the previous requirements. Thus, the real size of the cells projected on the ground is computed by using the values from Table 1.a-b, resulting in squared cells with 32.16 m sides. The number of photographs required to map the agricultural field are obtained by taking into account this value and the information given in the Table 1.c. Therefore, the workspace is decomposed into 60 cells (6x10). Finally, the last parameter to be obtained is the quad-rotor flight altitude, which is computed by applying Equation 2, the values from Table 1.b and the previous computed real cell size τ_d . The altitude τ_d computed turned out to be 45.94 m (~ 46 m).

Moreover, as there are areas that do not need to be covered, it means that there are points with no information of interest. They are points where the quad-rotor does not have to pass. These points could be a pond, a patch without cultivation or with some kind of agricultural infrastructure or machinery inside. After defining which are and which are not the points within the environment to be considered for mapping, the mission planner computes the flight trajectory as detailed in the section Path generation.

Fig. 8: Path generated by the mission planner.

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The vineyard parcel is shown decomposed in a grid-based fashion in figure 8. From 60 cells, 25% were not considered in the coverage trajectory. The coverage path was computed by considering initial and final positions, which are typically near the base station where all equipment and ground personal are located. The red square on the picture depicts the base station location in the grid. Furthermore, the blue dotted line represents a small trajectory carried by the quad-rotor after finishing the coverage mission and coming to the initial (as well as the final) point of the mission (return home procedure).

The coverage trajectory depicted in figure 8 can be sent to the quad-rotor and then the mission is carried out. In addition to the X and Y co-ordinates, the Z has to be set corresponding to the computed height. An offset of 9 m was added to the vehicle height in order to compensate height estimation accuracy and ensure overlapping rate. Moreover, cruise speed was set to 3 m/s. The real trajectory performed by the quad-rotor is shown in figure 9 (blue solid line). The resulting coverage path relies on 21 turns with predefined start and goal positions. The overall heading rotation cost can be expressed as,

$$\Gamma = 4 \times \Gamma_{135^\circ} + 13 \times \Gamma_{90^\circ} + 4 \times \Gamma_{45^\circ} + 28 \times \Gamma_{0^\circ} \quad (8)$$

1 The overall coverage mission was accomplished in 660s, with 82% of effective
 2 aerial coverage and 18% of system assessment and ground station setup. A set of
 3 metrics obtained after flight is summed up in table 2.
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 6 Fig. 9: Quadrotor real flight trajectory over the vineyard parcel.

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 8 Table 2: Results obtained in the coverage mission.

Metrics measured after flight					
Turns	Coverage time	Setup time	Path length	Height	Speed
	(s)	(s)	(m)	(m)	(m/s)
21	540	120	1546	55	3

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 10 Typical coverage patterns denoted as Serpentine or Back-and-forth
 11 motions are often used in agriculture since they are easy to compute. However,
 12 they become inefficient trajectories when irregular shape fields are considered.

13 In order to evaluate the reduction in time required for the coverage by
 14 using different types of planners, three different solutions have been considered.
 15 A basic Serpentine algorithm, a “smart” serpentine algorithm (that takes into
 16 account the returning home path in order not to repeat some waypoints) and
 17 finally, the proposed approach.

18 Considering the mission time required by the basic serpentine algorithm
 19 as reference, the smart serpentine has achieved a reduction of 14% and a reduction
 20 of 27% for the proposed algorithm. The number of cells without interest that the

1 drone visited using basic serpentine algorithm was 15%. Nevertheless, this
2 number strongly depends on the shape of the field.

3 Furthermore, the main advantage of the proposed algorithm is not only the
4 reduction in mission time but also the flexibility for its use in large areas with
5 irregular shapes. These areas can include points of no interest such as
6 greenhouses, lakes or rivers. The proposed approach allows the drones to perform
7 their task in a fully automated manner and reduce the time that drones are out of
8 the target field to a minimum.

9 **Image acquisition and mosaicing**

10 In the last stage of the process, all resources generated in previous phases have to
11 be combined. As a result, a global image of the current environment could be
12 obtained by joining the set of images acquired during the flight. Nevertheless, due
13 to the errors set by the real operation, a sequential combination of the photographs
14 is not enough. In order to get good performance, both image pre-processing and
15 post-processing are necessary. On the other hand, accurate methods are usually
16 complex and slow. They do not allow real time responses, as needed for example
17 in robot co-operation. Thus, a method to increase handling speed is advisable. In
18 order to achieve this, a refinement process has been implemented in four simple
19 steps. It takes advantage of their individual simplicity for providing a faster
20 response.

21 The first step starts with navigation data analysis that allows performing
22 the initial image alignment: whenever a photograph is taken, the quad-rotor
23 associates the information in the flight registers with the picture acquired at that
24 moment. These data, provided by the Flight Control System (FCS), are not only
25 made of GPS co-ordinates, but also orientation and attitude estimation. Despite
26 errors and bias, the correlation of this information allows placing every
27 photograph in a relative sketch. Figure 10 presents the results obtained in the first
28 approach. Although the images are correctly placed, it can be observed that many
29 crop rows do not match. That is due to the measurement and calibration errors,
30 which are inherent to the system.

31 The definition of a maximum error allowed threshold imposes the
32 maximum displacement on the mosaicing process. Additionally, it could also be

1 observed that different exposure levels make matching process and posterior
2 identification attempts difficult.

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5 Fig. 10: Photographic superposition based only on the flight data provided by the quad-rotor. On
6 the left, image borders are shown in order to highlight the position and orientation of each one. On
7 the right, the resulting image where no correspondence in rows can be appreciated.

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9 The second step consists of rectifying the deformations and distortions
10 derived from the drone's attitude in the acquisition time: non-zero roll and pitch
11 angles require a projection correction in order to compensate the vertical drift. In
12 such manner, the acquisition height has to be considered since projection error is
13 directly related to the flight altitude.

14 The correction has been done using PanoTools and Hugin's Batch
15 Processor algorithm (German et al. 2007). This method warps each image
16 according to its attitude parameters. An equi-rectangular approach has been
17 chosen, with a horizontal field of view (HFOV) of 67.9 and a barrel factor of
18 0.00005. Table 3 summarizes the angles estimated for five continuous
19 photographs. The corrections, adapted according to Philpot (2001), prompt a
20 collection of overlapped images (see figure 11), which are the starting point for
21 the third step.

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24 Fig. 11: Three examples of different stitching steps. The image set used in each step is highlighted
25 in different colors.

1 After correcting the distortion, the resulting image has to be remapped on
 2 the tangent plane, avoiding the lens deviation. Considering that almost all
 3 deviations occur radially, towards or away from some common center, a radial
 4 correction was applied considering the following third degree polynomial for
 5 describing the distortion:

$$6 \quad r_{src} = (a r_{dest}^3 + b r_{dest}^2 + c r_{dest} + d) r_{dest} \quad (9)$$

7
 8 where r_{src} and r_{dest} refer to the normalized radius of an image pixel (source and
 9 destiny radius, respectively). The values of the parameters that resolve $r_{src} = r_{dest}$
 10 were obtained experimentally: $a=0.22886$, $b=-0.42509$ and $c=0.37991$. The ‘d’
 11 parameter was omitted since it is related to the aspect ratio.

12 In the same way, the second step implies an adjustment in terms of
 13 photometry (Philpot 2001): The exposure and white balance are adapted in each
 14 image in order to generate a homogeneous composition. Table 3 column 4 shows
 15 the exposure value (EV) calculated for five consecutive images. It has been used
 16 as an EMoR (empirical model of response) .

17
 18 Table 3: Correction parameters for quad-rotor's attitude compensation.

Image	Yaw	Pitch	Roll	EV
0	-0.052	-0.002	0.986	13.3
1	72.176	0.04	1.015	13.2
2	33.76	0.035	1.505	13.1
3	35.43	0.119	1.135	13.8
4	34.64	0.008	1.055	13.6

26
 27 In addition to this, other effects make difficult the association process,
 28 such as the vignetting effect (Aggarwal et al. 2001) that takes into account the
 29 falloff in the corners of the images produced by a lens. The radiance filter
 30 implemented in Panotools (Senore 2004) was used in order to compensate this
 31 effect.

32 The following step (3rd) supposes a refinement of the previous ones. It is
 33 based on the visual correlation between the overlapped images and allows the

1 alignment of the photographs taken by identifying significant points between pairs
2 of images (D'Angelo 2007). This process is a stand-alone mosaicing method.
3 Nevertheless, it is not very advisable or efficient considering the large collection
4 of images that the algorithm has to deal with. Furthermore, low visual disparity
5 (the pictures are quite similar) makes the process even more time-consuming
6 without the capability of providing an unambiguous solution.

7 However, complexity would be exponentially reduced if the alignment
8 process were only applied to the images found in a reduced area. In such manner,
9 the algorithm tries only to match neighboring images, structured in this way
10 according to the results of the previous steps. Thus, only a local search is required,
11 focusing on the adjacent borders. The coincidences found define a concrete
12 relation (orientation, location and perspective) between each pair of images. It
13 enables the algorithm to adjust both the EV and the orientation of the images,
14 considering both areas as homogeneous from that moment.

15 The uniform area increases its size for each iteration until the entire field is
16 considered. Nevertheless, there is also a secondary global post process which
17 considers the relation between photographs in a global way. This technique allows
18 reducing exaggerated distortions in the last images which have been derived from
19 a daisy chain distortion transmission. Using this algorithm, the fine adjustment of
20 the orientation for each image is sped up and it thereby reduces failure rate.

21 The two horizontal examples presented in figure 12 illustrate how the
22 control-points search method works: Based on the scale-invariant feature
23 transform (SIFT) algorithm (Lowe 1999, Ke and Sukthankar 2004), the program
24 correlates similar (identical) physical features in order to establish the relative
25 camera orientations mathematically.

26

1
2 Fig. 12: Two examples of pairs of images related by control points. The highlighted points have
3 been selected by SIFT algorithm and used in order to determine relative rotation between the
4 related images.

5
6 In the last step, visually-enhanced algorithms have been used for
7 improving the mosaic quality and fusion. The manual adjustment of
8 sharpening, contrast and color temperature has allowed highlighting of the
9 crop rows and plants in the scenario. It makes characteristic recognition
10 easier. Softening and blurring algorithms have been also applied in order
11 to smooth the borders between images. Figure 13 shows the final
12 composition after implementing these techniques. It should be considered
13 that the inner area without coverage (highlighted with the red circle) is the
14 area prohibited in the path planning. Absence of data is thereby fully
15 justified.

16

1

2

Fig. 13: Final composition after applying the visual enhancing algorithms.

3

4

Finally, as a verification process, the resulting image has been compared with the one expected (provided by other GIS systems). In this case, a matching process has been carried out with the satellite image (see figure 14). It has allowed a fine adjustment in the geo-referencing of the mosaic. Thus, some minor errors in the perspective, due to bias in the calibration of the system, have also been corrected.

10

11

12

Fig. 14: Comparison between the generated image and the expected one, provided by a GIS system

1 **Conclusions**

2 In this paper, a complete tool that allows aerial image mosaicing with low
3 cost components has been presented. A novel path-planning tool, which produces
4 near-optimal trajectories applicable to many different commercial UAVs, has
5 been developed. A detailed study of the main problems in selecting and installing
6 the cameras onboard has been carried out. A complete mission definition
7 example has also been provided. Experimental results including reliable and fast
8 mosaicing procedures have been presented.

9 This study proves that a complete aerial image of a large area can be
10 obtained by using small UAVs in a fast, affordable and reliable way.

11

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